

Positive control #1 of VACht staining (mouse gallbladder)

Positive control #2 of VACht staining (mouse pancreas)

Supplemental Fig. S4 (related to **Fig. 6**). **Vesicular acetylcholine transporter (VACht) tissue staining controls.** (A-G) Mouse gallbladder (positive control #1) vs. liver (negative in parenchyma). Asterisk in *B* is enlarged in *C* (mucosal folds). Projections in *C* (DAPI) and *D* (PGP9.5 and VACht signals) examine the same microenvironment. White, nuclei; magenta, pan-neuronal marker PGP9.5; yellow, parasympathetic marker VACht. In *D*, the liver parenchymal and gallbladder domains show PGP9.5⁺ VACht⁻ and PGP9.5⁺ VACht⁺ nerves, respectively. Arrow in *D* is enlarged in *E* and further enlarged in *F* and *G* to specify the PGP9.5⁺ VACht⁺ parasympathetic nerve fibers. (H-Q) Mouse pancreas as a second positive control of VACht staining. H-M are panoramic views of pancreatic parenchyma and neuro-insular network. Arrow and asterisk indicate the area of interest, which is enlarged in N-Q. Note that both the exocrine and endocrine domains of pancreas are innervated by the parasympathetic nerves (M). Areas 1 and 2 in N are further enlarged in O-Q to specify the parasympathetic innervation of islet and acinus and the islet-ganglionic association.

Positive control #2 of VACht staining (mouse pancreas, continued)

Positive control #3 of VACht staining (human pancreas)

Positive control #3 of VACHT staining (human pancreas, continued)

Supplemental Fig. S4 (related to **Fig. 6**). **Vesicular acetylcholine transporter (VACHT) tissue staining controls, continued.** (R-Z) Human pancreas as a third positive control of VACHT staining. Boxes in *R* and *V* examine the same microenvironment, which is enlarged in *S-U* (intrapancreatic ganglion) and *W-Y* (islet and acinus) to identify the parasympathetic innervation (PGP9.5⁺ VACHT⁺ nerves, arrows). The Airyscan super-resolution imaging of intrapancreatic ganglion is presented in *Z*. *Z*₁-*Z*₃ show three optical sections of the PGP9.5⁺ ganglion (magenta). *Z*₂ is further enlarged in *Z*₄ to specify the neuronal nucleus (white arrow) and VACHT⁺ varicosities (yellow arrows). White, DAPI; depth of optical section, 0.5 μm.